

Chapter 3. How does business impact biodiversity?¹

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This chapter should be cited as: Mandle L., Kohsaka R., Bull J., Crona B., Johnston M.A., Oguge N.O., Panwar R., Romero C., Avila-Ortega D.I., Chelangat S. Chetty K., Vargas-Rayó O. (2026). **Chapter 3: How does business impact biodiversity?** In: Methodological Assessment Report of the Impact and Dependence of Business on Biodiversity and Nature's Contributions to People of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. Rueda X., Jones M., Polasky S., (eds.). IPBES secretariat, Bonn, Germany. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17074410>

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Executive summary

1. The activities of businesses and financial institutions have had significant impacts on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people, through a variety of pathways across the full value chain of businesses (*well established*) {3.1, 3.2, 3.3, 3.4, 3.5}. Understanding business impacts on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people is needed to guide decision-making by businesses, financial institutions, governments, consumers and civil society, to manage these impacts and their associated risks and opportunities, and to promote accountability and transparency (*well established*) {3.5, 3.6}.

2. Business activities impact biodiversity and nature's contributions to people by contributing to the drivers of biodiversity change and affecting the state of nature (*well established*) {3.2}. Businesses have direct, value chain, and indirect impacts on biodiversity. Business activities, in combination with other societal activities, also have cumulative impacts. While the impacts of business activities on biodiversity have been overwhelmingly negative, they can in some cases be positive relative to the current state of biodiversity. Positive impacts will need to become frequent and substantial to halt and reverse biodiversity loss to meet the goals of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework. Business impacts on nature's contributions to people are complex, increasing the production of certain material contributions, such as agricultural products, while reducing regulating and non-material contributions.

3. All businesses have impacts on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people linked to their activities and value chains. The magnitude and form of a business's impact vary based on the type, scale (spatial and temporal), magnitude, frequency and location of their activities (*well established*) {3.2}. Impacts result from businesses' physical activities, such as using raw materials and energy to produce goods, and non-physical activities, such as influencing consumer demand for goods and services.

4. Business impacts on biodiversity affect everyone, but Indigenous Peoples and local communities, women, children and the rural poor are among those particularly susceptible to harms (*well established*) {3.2, 3.5}. The effects of business impacts on biodiversity on these and other vulnerable groups can be positive or negative, although the preponderance of impacts to date have been negative (*well established*) {3.2, 3.5}. These vulnerable groups are especially susceptible to negative impacts from businesses in part because of their direct interrelationships with nature and their reliance on common-pool resources.

5. A diversity of methods for identifying impacts of businesses on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people is available, both within the scientific literature and for practical applications (*well established*) {3.3}. No single method or metric can capture all dimensions of impact (*well established*) {3.2, 3.3}. Different methods focus on different components of biodiversity (e.g., ecosystems, species) or different aspects of nature's contributions to people (e.g., regulation of climate, regulation of freshwater quality), or use proxy indicators (e.g., emissions, resource use). Some methods rely on location-based observations of nature, while others use modelling. Approaches produce a mix of qualitative and quantitative measures. Methods differ in their ability to capture variation in impacts by location, within sectors and across the value chain.

6. Existing methods have not yet produced a comprehensive and comparable attribution of impacts across all sectors or businesses (*well established*) {3.3, 3.4}. However, current analyses point to agriculture, forestry and fishing as sectors with large negative impacts on biodiversity, particularly given contributions to land use change (*established but incomplete*) {3.4}. The highest quantified impacts come from sectors that produce materials and energy in response to demand from other sectors and consumers, and so ultimately all sectors contribute to these impacts through their value chains (*established but incomplete*) {3.2, 3.4}. Other sectors found to have relatively high impacts on biodiversity and materiality across multiple studies include energy (electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply sector), construction, mining and quarrying, transportation and storage, and manufacturing. In terms of nature's contributions to people, sectors such as agriculture, forestry and fishing have increased certain material contributions from nature (such as food and timber) but have had negative impacts on other nature's contributions to people, such as regulating contributions.

7. Comparable global estimates of sector-level impacts on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people are hindered by inaccessible data on the location and magnitude of business activities, a lack of traceability of material flows and impacts through value chains, and the use of different metrics produced by incompatible methods (*well established*) {3.4}. Voluntary self-disclosure by businesses has not yet yielded enough data to support such analyses. Other key knowledge gaps at the sector level include impacts on nature's contributions to people across sectors, as well as the potential for positive impacts on biodiversity relative to current conditions, both of which could be relatively high for agriculture, forestry and fishing compared to other sectors (*established but incomplete*) {3.4}. Improving estimates of business- and sector-level impacts on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people requires filling gaps in data on the location and type of business activities, improving traceability of impacts across value chains, and implementing comparable proxies where drivers are understood across sectors.

9. Businesses face nature-related risks and opportunities resulting both from their impacts and their dependencies on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people (*well established*) {3.5}. Risks can arise from a business's impacts on resources on which it depends, such as unsustainable harvest; from business impacts that occur separate from its dependencies, such as from pollution or land conversion; or from activities of actors outside the business's value chain, such as government regulation. Risks can be categorized as physical, transition or systemic risks. Businesses may also find nature-related opportunities to offer new products and services; to secure or enhance the biodiversity on which they depend; to differentiate themselves in the marketplace; and to face fewer regulatory pressures; and to manage liability by reducing negative impacts or contributing to positive impacts on biodiversity. The way businesses choose to manage their impacts and dependencies significantly influences their risk and opportunity landscape.

10. The impacts of the informal economy on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people are substantial and important to recognize but understudied (*established but incomplete*) {3.4}. The informal economy may be included in assessments of business impacts that focus on activities detectable from satellite imagery, such as mining, agriculture and logging. Other informal activities, such as wild plant harvest, are more difficult to assess through these methods. The interface between the informal economy and formal economy is important to consider, given flows of materials between them and the size of the informal economy. Indigenous Peoples and local communities have both a high participation rate in the

informal economy and a susceptibility to harms from the negative impacts of the informal economy on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people.

11. Actions to improve the ability to systematically and comparably quantify business impacts on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people would enable more effective policy and management to reduce or reverse the loss of biodiversity (*well established*) {3.6}. To date, the limited quantitative comparable estimates of both the tangible and intangible impacts on biodiversity from different businesses and sectors have a range of implications for decision-making by businesses, financial institutions, consumers, governments and civil society. The multiple pathways by which business activities affect biodiversity and nature's contributions to people have made it challenging to adopt consistent methodologies for quantifying the impacts – and hence multiple methodologies and metrics are currently being applied. While there is no one-size-fits-all measurement approach across sectors, comparable and systematic approaches are needed while considering local issues. The development of scenarios, understanding trade-offs, including distributional impacts, and more widespread use of tools and measurements would help inform different stakeholders on making appropriate decisions and action to enable transformative change.

3.1. Introduction

Global acceleration of unsustainable economic activity over the past century is driving a loss of biodiversity and undermining Earth's life support systems (IPBES, 2019b). The activities of businesses and financial institutions have collectively had significant negative impacts on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people, through a variety of pathways across the full value chain of businesses (Bruyninckx et al., 2024; Dasgupta, 2021; IPBES, 2019a). At the same time, impacts of businesses vary greatly in terms of their intensity, duration, magnitude, frequency and reversibility, as a factor of business activity type, location and other properties. Impacts of businesses on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people can also have profound effects on Indigenous Peoples and local communities (IPLCs) and other vulnerable groups with significant direct interrelationships with biodiversity and on Indigenous and local knowledge that is typically intertwined with local ecosystems and biodiversity. An understanding of the type, magnitude and extent of businesses' and financial institutions' impacts is key to informing decisions by consumers, investors, business leaders and policy makers. While impacts can already be managed without comprehensive measurement, the ability to accurately measure these impacts and attribute them to specific business activities is critical to promoting transparency, accountability and action.

Chapter 3 assesses business impact types and pathways and describes the methods available for measuring them. It builds on the definitions of businesses and sectors established in **Chapter 1** and the assessment of business dependencies in **Chapter 2**. This chapter sets the foundation for an assessment of the suitability of approaches for levels of business decision-making to assess impacts and dependencies (**Chapter 4**) and of options for action that follow both for businesses (**Chapter 5**) and for governments, the financial system and other actors (**Chapter 6**).

This chapter is organized as follows:

Section 3.2 presents a framework for understanding the pathways by which businesses impact biodiversity and nature's contributions to people and a typology of impact types. This typology includes direct, value chain, indirect and cumulative impacts.

Section 3.3 reviews available approaches and tools for measuring businesses' impacts on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people, highlighting shared features and key differences across options.

Section 3.4 synthesizes and evaluates the current state of knowledge of impacts by sector based on existing methods for measuring impact.

Section 3.5 examines the connections between business impacts and dependencies on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people, as well as links to business risks and opportunities.

Section 3.6 assesses the implications of business impacts – and the current state of the ability to measure these impacts – on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people on decision-making by governments, businesses, the financial system, and other actors (including civil society, consumers and IPLCs).

Throughout the chapter, each section discusses connections to IPLCs and other vulnerable groups. Finally, the chapter identifies key gaps in knowledge, data and methodologies

Methodological assessment of the impact and dependence of business on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people
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(Annex B), highlighting needs for data collection and data sharing and opportunities for new research and collaboration efforts.

3.2. Pathways and typology of impacts

3.2.1. Pathways by which businesses impact biodiversity

Businesses impact biodiversity and nature's contributions to people through changes in land and sea use, direct exploitation of organisms, climate change, pollution, and the introduction of invasive alien species, among other drivers (**Figure 3.1**) (IPBES, 2019a). Business activities contribute to driving biodiversity change through, for example, deforestation for industrial agricultural activities, land-use change from mining or infrastructure development such as roads, dams and waterways, degradation due to resource extraction such as timber harvesting and the spread of invasive alien species through transportation and shipping. There is not yet a consistent terminology for referring to these drivers of biodiversity change. The IPBES Global Assessment of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES, 2019a) refers to these as the most important 'direct drivers of biodiversity loss'. The drivers of biodiversity change correspond to 'pressures' within the Driver, Pressure, State, Impact, Response (DPSIR) framework used in the environmental assessment field and adopted by the Science-Based Targets Network (Science Based Targets Network, 2023). Finally, they are also referred to as "impact drivers" by groups including the Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures (TNFD, 2023) and the Capitals Coalition (Natural Capital Coalition, 2016).

Drivers of biodiversity change are affected by socioeconomic trends, which include changes in demographics and sociocultural characteristics, economic and technological developments, evolving institutional and governance systems and issues like conflicts and epidemics (IPBES, 2019a) (**Figure 3.1**). The IPBES Global Assessment (IPBES, 2019a) refers to these as "indirect drivers" of biodiversity change. The IPBES Transformative Change Assessment further identifies underlying causes of biodiversity change, including disconnection from and domination over biodiversity and people, concentration of power and wealth and prioritization of short-term individual and material gains (IPBES, 2024). Business activities are both shaped by and contribute to these socioeconomic trends and their underlying causes, often in complex and unpredictable ways. Business activities may influence political and economic systems at all scales, such as through swaying government policies via lobbying, through philanthropic contributions to conservation organizations, by influencing consumer preferences and affecting the supply-demand dynamics of products and services. For instance, marketing and sales activities can stimulate consumerism (Abela, 2006) and reshape a society's sociocultural makeup. Similarly, activities in the supply-chain domain, especially those involving distributed natural resource supply networks, can lead to community conflicts (Deberdt & Billon, 2021; Hofmann et al., 2018; Murcia et al., 2021) and the spread of zoonotic diseases (Tumelty et al., 2023). Business practices in human resource management can influence local demographics (Zhang et al., 2019), while stakeholder management strategies, particularly through lobbying, can alter institutions and governance systems (Clapp, 2021; Madsen & Ulhøi, 2001; Savell et al., 2014). While these linkages are conceptually well-supported, quantifying their extent and the subsequent impact on biodiversity is difficult.

Understanding the impacts of operations and supply chain activities on drivers of biodiversity change tends to be more straightforward than for activities such as marketing and finance (Ghadge et al., 2020; Howard-Grenville et al., 2014). Examples of this are the connections between operations and supply chain activities and drivers like climate change or the introduction of invasive alien species (Borgelt et al., 2024; Hulme et al., 2018). These activities are also more clearly linked to land and sea use changes and the exploitation of organisms – areas where extensive assessment and modelling efforts have been conducted, particularly in

sectors such as agriculture, forestry, and infrastructure development (Kasraian et al., 2016; Lambin et al., 2000; Lambin & Meyfroidt, 2011; Lark et al., 2017). Meanwhile, the effects of financial activities (Pástor et al., 2022; Vörösmarty et al., 2018) and marketing practices (Galeazzo et al., 2014; Klassen & Vachon, 2003; Moran & Kanemoto, 2016; Ottman, 2017) on biodiversity loss are receiving growing attention. However, the understanding of impacts remains largely conceptual and are not yet as systematically measured or understood.

The magnitude and form of a business's impact vary based on the type, scale (spatial and temporal), magnitude, frequency and location of its business activities. Business activities can affect all components of biodiversity, from genes to species to communities to ecosystems (Panwar et al., 2023). The same business activity will have varying consequences for biodiversity and ecosystem functioning depending on the ecosystem and climate zone where impacts occur (Benítez-López et al., 2010; Bobbink et al., 2010; Li & Jiang, 2021; Mantyka-Pringle et al., 2011). Business activities can also impact all forms of nature's contributions to people, including material, regulating and non-material benefits. Business impacts on nature's contributions to people also include intergenerational impacts (Hayward et al., 2022). The impacts of business activities on nature's contributions to people often occur as a result of their negative impacts on biodiversity. For example, nutrient pollution from agricultural and industrial activity around the Black Sea led to a hypoxic zone and fish die-off in the 1970s and 80s, during which period the \$2 billion commercial fishery declined by 90 percent (Rabotyagov et al., 2014). However, businesses can also have impacts on nature's contributions to people without an associated loss of biodiversity. This can occur when a business reduces people's ability to access nature's contributions to people, such as through implementation of conservation measures meant to protect biodiversity that restrict access to land for wild plant harvest and other activities (Bidaud et al., 2017).

Overall, the impacts of business activities on the state of biodiversity and nature's contributions to people through drivers of biodiversity change have been overwhelmingly negative. This is evidenced by the global decline in biodiversity and its diminished capacity to provide sustained contributions to people (IPBES, 2019a). When business activities enhance biodiversity and nature's contributions to people relative to current levels, these impacts may be considered positive (**Figure 3.2**). Such instances of positive impacts are currently rare. Many claims of positive outcomes are more accurately described as reductions in negative impacts rather than genuine positive contributions relative to a reference state (**Section 3.2, 3.**).

3.2.2. 31 Typology of business impacts on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people: direct, value chain, indirect and cumulative

The multi-faceted properties of business impacts – across space, time, the value chain and business activity type – have led to varied categorizations and terminology. Sometimes, the literature distinguishes business impacts on biodiversity based on whether the business organization's boundaries are defined narrowly or broadly: the former are known as business-level impacts, while the latter are referred to as value chain level impacts (Crenna et al., 2020; Maier et al., 2019; Panwar, 2023). Some impacts occur locally – that is, close to the site of business operations and others occur remotely due to the activities of others in the value chain. Business impacts on biodiversity are often examined only in relation to the production processes involved in creating a product. However, they may also be assessed across the product's entire life (Damiani et al., 2023; Wolff et al., 2017) .

By examining both the pathways by which an individual business contributes to the loss of biodiversity and nature's contributions to people, along with the scope of analysis, a primary

typology of impacts emerges as direct, value chain and indirect impacts (**Figure 3.1**). All impacts of a particular business ultimately result from that business's effects on the drivers of biodiversity change; what differentiates them is the degree to which that effect is directly under the business's control. A business's direct impacts result from operational business activities like mining and drilling for resources, clearing forests or other vegetation, farming, manufacturing and transporting and selling goods. A business's value chain impacts result from the impacts of its upstream or downstream value chain on drivers of biodiversity change. Indirect impacts result from activities that were spurred by that business's actions but fall beyond its direct operations or value chain. For example, development of a mine often leads to in-migration to the surrounding area, with expansion of transportation and energy infrastructure (Giljum et al., 2022). These impacts are indirect from the perspective of the mine operator but have real consequences for biodiversity and nature's contributions to people that are linked to the mine's operations.

The accumulation of impacts and their interactions in a location over time give rise to a crucial secondary form of impact known as cumulative impacts (sometimes referred to as "aggregate impacts") (IPBES, 2023; Wassénus et al., 2024; Whitehead et al., 2017). Cumulative impacts occur when the impacts of multiple businesses and other actors in an area have additive or interactive effects that are greater than would be expected from their individual activities occurring in isolation. Considering such cumulative impacts is essential for fully assessing a business's impacts on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people.

The level and scope of analysis are critical when analysing the impacts of business activities on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people (**Figure 3.1**). A narrow analysis considers only business- or operations-level activities and their associated impacts. A broader analysis includes value chain-level activities and impacts. Corporate reporting practices often overlook this more comprehensive approach due to challenges with data availability and the complexity of methods, yet it is vital for developing effective corporate strategies to achieve global biodiversity targets (Panwar, 2023). Notably, business size – whether measured by the number of employees or revenue – is not a definitive factor in determining business impacts on biodiversity. While larger businesses may in general have greater impacts on biodiversity, business size alone is not a sufficient proxy for quantifying a business's impacts or comparing impacts among businesses.

Figure 3.1. Typology and pathways of business impacts on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people. Businesses have direct, value chain, indirect, and cumulative impacts on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people through their impacts on drivers of biodiversity change and socioeconomic trends. Direct impacts stem from the operational activities of a business, while value chain impacts result from the activities within its upstream or downstream value chain. Indirect impacts result from activities that were spurred by that business's actions but fall beyond its direct operations or value chain, such as population growth, land clearing and the expansion of infrastructure surrounding a new mine or road. Cumulative impacts result from the aggregate effects of businesses and other actors at a site, landscape or seascape, or globally.

3.2.3. Positive impacts of business activities on biodiversity

While business activities typically have negative impacts on biodiversity, there are instances where they can have a positive impact relative to the current state of biodiversity. A clearly defined baseline and consistent identification and measurement of impacts are necessary to differentiate reductions in negative impacts on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people from those with a positive impact on their state (Figure 3.2). For instance, certain agriculture and forestry practices can genuinely enhance biodiversity compared to current levels, thus qualifying as positive impacts (e.g., Torralba et al., 2016). However, if a business adopts waste reduction strategies that alleviate the drive for further land use change, this only reduces its negative impact, rather than constituting a positive impact on the state of biodiversity relative to current conditions.

Figure 3.2. Differentiating positive and negative impacts of business activities on biodiversity. Whether the impacts of business activities on biodiversity can be considered positive or negative depends on the baseline conditions against which these impacts are measured (grey dot and dashed line). Activities such as restoration of ecosystems or agricultural practices that enhance biodiversity can have positive impacts (green arrow) that improve the state of biodiversity relative to a baseline of current conditions. Activities that lead to more efficient land use or reduced waste production can lessen the ongoing negative impacts of business activities (orange arrow), leading to improved outcomes relative to a business-as-usual scenario (blue arrow) but without improving the state of biodiversity relative to a baseline of current conditions. When considered against a relatively unimpacted reference state, the impacts of business activities on biodiversity will nearly always be negative.

Recent surges in corporate claims to achieving no net loss or net positive impacts on biodiversity (De Silva et al., 2019) and proliferation of the term “regenerative” in corporate sustainability literature (Feger & Mermet, 2022; Hahn & Tampe, 2021; Konietzko et al., 2023; Muñoz & Branzei, 2021) therefore warrant a clear distinction between actions that reduce negative impacts and those that are positive. When measured against a baseline of an “intact,” “pristine,” or otherwise unimpacted reference state, the impacts of business activities on biodiversity will be nearly exclusively negative. In addition, combining positive and negative impacts into a measure of “net” impacts risks masking important negative impacts, given the location specificity of impacts to biodiversity and nature’s contributions to people. Claims of no net loss

or net positive impacts therefore warrant careful attention to the underlying negative and positive components.

3.2.4. Intersection of impacts with Indigenous Peoples and local communities and other vulnerable groups

The losses of biodiversity and nature's contributions to people affect everyone, but the burden of these losses is disproportionately borne by IPLCs and other vulnerable groups. Business activities impact biodiversity and nature's contributions to people in ways that negatively affect IPLCs through diverse and complex pathways connected to their strong and direct interrelationship with biodiversity (Kennedy et al., 2023). Often, these impacts manifest through reduced wildlife populations, water disruption and contamination of water and food sources, ultimately leading to food and water insecurity, cultural and livelihood disruptions and harm to cultural and spiritual practices. Women and girls are particularly vulnerable to these changes and may experience increased work burden, loss of income, decreased health, and increased exposure to gender-based violence as a result (Awumbila & Momsen, 1995; Booker et al., 2022, 2022; Treviño & Murillo-Sandoval, 2021). Children, especially in rural areas and less-developed communities, are also at heightened risk for health impacts (Herrera et al., 2017; Rasolofoson et al., 2018, 2020). Individuals who oppose the environmental impacts associated with business activities have faced violence and assassination, particularly associated with conflicts around resource extraction, land use and water management (Scheidel et al., 2020). Such violence disproportionately affects – but is not limited to – Indigenous Peoples (Scheidel et al., 2020).

Paradoxically, these effects often arise from business involvement in climate transition strategies, such as mineral extraction for electric vehicle production, plantation schemes to support carbon offset projects or biodiversity offset programs (Bidaud et al., 2017; Owen et al., 2022). This phenomenon, known as the green-green dilemma (Voigt et al., 2019), is emerging as a key social justice issue in climate transition strategies, as nearly 69 per cent of existing or planned critical mineral projects worldwide are located on or near IPLC lands (Stark, 2024).

Interweaving Indigenous and local knowledge with scientific practices and decision-making could provide actionable strategies to safeguard IPLCs from the negative biodiversity impacts of businesses. However, the way this incorporation is sought could itself undermine Indigenous knowledge systems (Gazing Wolf et al., 2024). Corporate-led efforts to respect and learn from IPLCs are also increasing. However, due caution is warranted, as these initiatives can become tools of appropriation. Financial institutions can play a crucial role in protecting IPLCs from business impacts on biodiversity especially by requiring project planners to meaningfully engage IPLCs in project planning and implementation with their free, prior and informed consent (Sperl, 2024).

3.3. How impacts are identified

3.3.1. Approaches to impact measurement

A large variety of approaches have been developed to identify and measure business impacts (or proxies for impact) on biodiversity and nature’s contributions to people. These approaches can be classified according to the same typology of approaches used to measure dependencies (see **Chapter 2**). Following **Chapter 2**, these approaches can be grouped into five broad categories: biophysical approaches, economic-ecological modelling, participatory mapping and monitoring methods, socio-cultural valuation and monetary valuation (**Table 3.1**). Biophysical approaches can be further divided into three sub-categories, given differences in their implications for informing decision-making by businesses and others: location-based observations, spatial analysis and modelling and life cycle approaches (**Table 3.1**). See **Chapter 4** for a more detailed evaluation of these impact measurement approaches and their suitability for informing different decision contexts.

Table 3.1. Overview of commonly used approaches for measuring impacts of business activities on biodiversity and nature’s contributions to people (adapted from Table 2.2 in Chapter 2), with illustrative examples of their application from the scientific literature. Note that the approach categories are not mutually exclusive, and example applications may integrate methods from across multiple approach categories.

Approaches	Example applications
Biophysical approaches	
Location-based observations	Field sampling used to measure the abundance and diversity of birds, plants, insects and spiders across crop fields of varying sizes in Canada (Fahrig et al., 2015) Satellite imagery used to quantify the direct and indirect impacts of industrial mines on deforestation across the tropics (Giljum et al., 2022)
Spatial analysis and modelling	Different potential power line routes overlaid with environmental and social data layers to measure the routes’ impacts on ecologically sensitive and socially complex areas in South Africa (Warner & Diab, 2002). Global modelling of nature’s contributions to people and biodiversity combined with asset locations to quantify the direct impacts of corporate assets from over 2,000 businesses (Mandle et al., 2024a).
Life cycle approaches	Life cycle assessment and environmentally extended multi-regional input-output models combined to estimate biodiversity impacts across a global set of 3,000 businesses (Kulionis et al., 2024). Life cycle assessment integrated with spatial modelling to assess the impacts of alternative feedstock sources for bioplastics from the USA and Brazil on biodiversity and nature’s contributions to people (Chaplin-Kramer et al., 2017).

Economic-ecological modelling	
	Nested multiregional input-output (MRIO) models used to quantify the impacts of beef production on threatened animal species in Australia through local and global supply chains (Malik et al., 2022).
Participatory mapping and monitoring methods	
	Participatory mapping identified potential impacts of offshore wind farms to local fisheries and marine biodiversity in Brazil (Xavier et al., 2023) Community monitors and scientists collaborated to assess water pollution and its impacts downstream of a coal mine in Zimbabwe (Ruppen et al., 2021).
Socio-cultural valuation	
	Choice experiment focus groups used to elicit ecosystem service and biodiversity values associated with different scenarios of shrimp aquaculture development and mangrove conservation in Vietnam (McDonough et al., 2014) The impacts of petroleum exploitation and agriculture on biodiversity and economically and medicinally useful plants in a forest reserve were documented using perception assessment in Nigeria (Udoma-Michaels et al., 2019)
Monetary valuation	
	Hedonic pricing used to value increases in property values, driven by reductions in local air pollutants and particulate matter from coal-to-gas conversion of power plants in China (Mei et al., 2021). Calculated net present value of public and private benefits of coastal protection and other ecosystem services from conservation of marshes surrounding a manufacturing facility in the U.S. (Reddy et al., 2015).

3.3.2. Impact measurement tools available to businesses and investors and their underlying assessment approaches

Approaches for measuring and estimating impacts of business activities on biodiversity and nature’s contributions to people (**Table 3.1**) are often combined into tools offering to help businesses, investors and other stakeholders assess impacts of businesses, including their investments. To understand what these tools do, the actual measurement methods and metrics used and how well they deliver on their ambitions, 28 approaches available at the time of this IPBES assessment’s initiation were reviewed (January 2024). This chapter refers to all these approaches as tools throughout **Sections 3.3.2** and **3.3.3**, although some offer a framework for assessment, rather than a specific methodology, yet are marketed as ‘tools’ to the business community². Tools included in the review state an aim to explicitly help businesses and

² Data management report referring to a review of biodiversity assessment approaches <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12790886>

financial institutions measure and report on their impacts on biodiversity or nature's contributions to people.

The selection of tools was based on an initial review of available tools online, starting from the collection of tools listed in the Assessment of Biodiversity Measurement Approaches for Businesses and Financial Institutions by the EU Business and Biodiversity Platform (Lammerant, 2021) and those listed in the Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures tool catalogue (TNFD, 2025). These lists were cross-checked against tools assessed in recent academic papers (Damiani et al., 2023; Zhu et al., 2024), and additional tools covered by these publications were added. The 28 tools included in the final review represent a broad range of tools available to the business and investment community for assessing impacts to biodiversity and nature's contributions to people at the time of writing this assessment but are not a comprehensive list. A detailed analysis of individual tools lies beyond the scope of this chapter. The purpose of the review is rather to assess the range of tools, provide an overview of the most commonly used approaches or combinations of approaches (see **Table 3.1**) on which they are based and briefly discuss the opportunities and pitfalls that these practices give rise to. The review is not intended as a comprehensive list, as the rapid evolution in the space of biodiversity impact assessment of business and finance would quickly make such a list outdated.

3.3.2.1. General trends

Tools were assessed across three dimensions: approach category (following **Table 3.1**), data used, and type of output metric. Tools included those focused on providing assessments of biodiversity-related risks to businesses or investments and those assessing impact. A detailed description of each tool, its methodology, the organization(s) behind its development, and intended users and suggested use (by developers) is available in the data management report.³ This analysis allowed authors to identify patterns regarding the specific dimensions of biodiversity impacts that each approach captured but also patterns in scientific traceability of the methodologies and approaches employed by tools.

Most tools (25 of 28) reviewed aim to provide some form of biodiversity-related impact assessment, while the remainder have a stronger focus on providing biodiversity-related risk assessments. The latter take a business-centric perspective on risk and analyses generally focus on understanding company or investor exposure to biodiversity impacts through their practices or through their supply chains. Risks can include those arising from high business dependencies on biodiversity, but also through reputational, regulatory or market risks related to the use of natural resources (see **Section 3.5**). As such, their primary concern is not with quantifying impacts on biodiversity from biodiversity loss *per se* but rather assessing how these impacts translate into business risk.

Tools vary in the number of drivers or pressures they considered in their analysis. Almost all tools include and are based on terrestrial drivers while freshwater and marine drivers are less prevalent. Similarly, extinction risk and invasive alien species are inconsistently covered. These findings align with results from recent research on similar sets of biodiversity assessment tools (Strange et al., 2024; Zhu et al., 2024). Using only land as an analytical entry point to assess impact is problematic considering the inherent complexity of biodiversity and the importance of and threats to freshwater and marine biodiversity. Recently, methods have

³ Data management report referring to a review of biodiversity assessment approaches <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12790886>

developed to include a greater number of drivers or pressures and integrate them with global extinction risk (Verones et al., 2020).

Most tools have individual businesses as their primary target audience (17 out of 28) and are intended to be used across various sectors (including agriculture, resource extraction and investments)⁴. Many remaining tools are designed for specific users or sectors and thus have a narrower range of applicability. These tools often have a high degree of scientific traceability, clearly articulated steps and good alignment between stated ambitions and outputs of the approach. Despite this, their specificity and more narrow scope mean they may be less versatile across different contexts, less scalable in their current form and currently not suitable for assessing and comparing businesses globally.

3.3.2.2. Methodological approaches applied

Most tools reviewed rely on a mix of approaches all falling under the broader category of 'biophysical approaches' outlined in **Table 3.1**. Variations of life cycle assessments are the most recurring methodology (10 out of 28) and are prominently represented by biodiversity footprinting tools (9 out of 10). These footprinting methodologies consistently use a combination of life cycle assessments and multiregional input-output analysis (MRIO) to calculate biodiversity impacts. This has been referred to as 'beyond life cycle assessments' because they add additional methodological components or economic-ecological modelling onto the overall life cycle assessment (Damiani et al., 2023). The biodiversity footprinting tools reviewed have many commonalities. Most can use business-specific data on pressures (drivers of biodiversity change such as land use, water, greenhouse gas emissions or pollution, depending on which life cycle assessment methodology is used). However, the review shows that because of the lack of business-specific asset level data, biodiversity impact assessments commonly use financial data in the form of business revenue reported at the headquarter level. These data are then connected to a multiregional input-output (MRIO) table to map links to other sectors and estimate the consumption of resources, and the emissions associated with each product or revenue stream (often referred to by the tools as 'capturing scope 3'). Such use of revenue data, coupled with multiregional input-output tables means that estimates of environmental pressures are not spatially explicit. Therefore, while biodiversity footprinting methods could produce results for different locations, as currently used they differ significantly from tools using 'spatial analysis and modelling' (**Table 3.1**) in their inability to deliver meaningful, location-specific information.

Environmental pressures estimated using multi-regional input-output tables are subsequently used as input into a life cycle assessment model. An underlying life cycle assessment method commonly used by reviewed tools is ReCiPe (Huijbregts et al., 2017). More recently developed life cycle approaches for biodiversity footprinting, including LC-IMPAC, cover global extinction risk as well as terrestrial, freshwater and marine pressures, but are not currently employed in the tools examined. Another model commonly used by existing tools is the global biodiversity model for policy support (referred to with the acronym "GLOBIO") (Schipper et al., 2020). This is not a life cycle assessment but is commonly used to derive characterization factors for this analytical step to allow for an estimate of impact in the form of mean species abundance or potentially disappeared fraction of species.

⁴ Data management report referring to a review of biodiversity assessment approaches (10.5281/zenodo.12790886).

Many footprinting tools rely on the same datasets. The most recurring pre-compiled datasets used by footprinting tools are Exiobase (an environmentally extended multiregional input-output database) and Ecoinvent (life cycle assessment database). Some footprinting tools rely on 'in-house' models or datasets and others require that tool users select which drivers of biodiversity impacts are considered on a case-by-case basis. Others require the user to choose which valuation methods to use. This means the robustness of expected outputs for a particular tool will depend on choices made by the user.

The second most common approach categories used by the tools reviewed are 'location-based observations' and 'spatial analysis and modelling' (**Table 3.1**), represented by 9 tools each. Tools using location-based observations often use land use and habitat as proxies for biodiversity or ecosystem services. Others use indicators against which to assess the operations or estimates of business-specific pressures, such as waste, land, water and other resource use. All rely in some way on business-specific information and thus reduce the issues of sector-generic outputs seen with footprinting tools, which cannot reliably inform actions of individual businesses.

Tools based on spatial analysis and modelling range from frameworks that combine biodiversity, ecosystem condition and natural capital accounting to support decision-making, map changes in ecosystems and how these likely affect the provision and value of ecosystem services or map likely biodiversity impact by overlaying business asset locations with various spatial datasets. Some of these tools in this category, including STAR (Species Threat Abatement and Restoration metric) and IBAT (Integrated Biodiversity Assessment Tool), rely on data extracted from the International Union for the Conservation of Nature Red List of Threatened Species. Others, like InVEST (Integrated Valuation of Ecosystem Services and Tradeoffs) rely on a combination of biophysical models, land use/land cover (LULC) data and other input data, and ecosystem service production functions from peer-reviewed ecological and economic research. The GLOBIO model, which features strongly in footprinting tools, is also employed in purely spatial analysis to provide impact appraisals of expected location-based activities.

The inclusion of monetary valuation, socio-cultural valuation and participatory mapping and monitoring approaches is limited across the tools reviewed. Only one tool (InVEST) includes monetary valuation approaches. InVEST can provide valuation of some impacts to biodiversity and nature's contributions to people by translating the biophysical outputs of ecosystem service models (e.g., quantity of water purified, coastlines protected, or carbon sequestered) into economic or social values. None of the tools reviewed explicitly incorporate socio-cultural valuation or perspectives of IPLCs, and none differentiate impacts on other vulnerable groups such as the urban or rural poor. However, some aspects of IPLC perspectives and differential social impacts can be incorporated into tools that rely on user-provided information. Several tools on the market also cannot be neatly classified into the approach categories covered in this report but instead tend more toward analysis of action strategies and corporate policy, monitoring compliance against standards and managing reputational risk.

The current landscape of tools available to businesses, investors and other actors for estimating business impacts on biodiversity is diverse. Biophysical approaches and economic-ecological modelling are the dominant methods in the set of tools reviewed, while participatory mapping and monitoring methods and socio-cultural valuation are not represented at all, and only one tool includes any aspect of monetary valuation. This highlights a divergence in focus between methodologies developed by science for understanding and assessing biodiversity and the methodologies business-oriented tools have thus far incorporated.

3.3.3 Challenges, limitations and potential issues of concern

Across the tools examined, a limited number of drivers or pressures tend to be included, as most tools reviewed assess only land-based impact. There is also limited diversity in the underlying models and datasets used to estimate impacts which means that any concerns or limitations relating to these data sources represent an inherent weakness that is replicated across all biodiversity assessment tools using them.

Tools reviewed here also display significant variability in the degree to which the scientific traceability of methods and assumptions is possible to discern. Some tools are very transparent and clear in their articulation of methodological steps and anchor their baselines clearly in public policy. Others have limited public documentation or are poorly referenced⁵. Broadly speaking, the tools produced by consultancies are more ambiguous in their methodological framework, less rigorously documented and are therefore more difficult to understand and evaluate. These tools often neglect to make explicit the causal connection between the driver they use to assess impact (most often land use change) and biodiversity. Insufficient public documentation also makes it hard to assess the validity of thresholds and indicators chosen and precludes evaluation of how capable the methodology is in delivering on the objectives of the tool. Tools also differ in the baselines they set, and these baselines are often not traceable to a scientific assessment or based on transparent scientific assumptions. Instead, the baseline is often understood to be the first occasion of measurements by a business, or the current state of biodiversity before some intervention.

A key concern pertaining specifically to biodiversity footprinting tool is that, as noted above, their current application often precludes spatially explicit impact assessments due to use of revenue data as inputs, reliance on sector averages and national level trade data. This is a major limitation given that the biodiversity impact of any specific business activity varies greatly based on its location across ecosystems and climate zones (see **Section 3.2.1**). Asset-level information on environmental pressures is therefore a necessary input for footprinting tools and outputs to inform business-specific mitigation goals and development of strategic action plans. Furthermore, the limited sector differentiation in environmentally extended input-output analysis (EEMRIO), and the fact that no positive impact information is currently available in these input-output tables, also means that biodiversity footprinting tools relying on MRIO analysis make identification of business-specific positive biodiversity impacts, and thus business opportunities, unattainable at present.

Against this background, it is noteworthy that tools geared at investors tend to be footprinting methods that do not rely on location-based observations. Several non-footprinting tools targeted at investors do employ some form of spatial analysis by providing opportunities to identify likely impacts and risks by overlaying spatial data with known locations. However, if operation-specific information of portfolio businesses is lacking and MRIO analysis is used to infer sector impacts, the same limitations apply as with footprinting tools.

The reviewed set of tools are also limited in their ability to effectively account for cumulative impact. Cumulative impacts include direct and indirect impacts, past, present and future, resulting from the actions of all actors, not just the target organization or project assessed. Cumulative impacts may arise from the actions of both public and private agents. This makes it difficult to assess in the context of a particular business. However, such impacts could be

⁵ Data management report referring to a review of biodiversity assessment approaches <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12790886>

assessed at the landscape, watershed, local government, state/provincial or national levels, as part of broader, non-organisational specific assessments.

This review of biodiversity assessment tools currently available highlights the need for a set of principles and best practices that all tools should adhere to in order to enable users to measure impacts in a way that can effectively accurately guide actions. These may first and foremost include transparent documentation, including clear scientific traceability and transparency regarding datasets and models used. It is important for tools to make explicit their assumptions about attribution and causality used to infer impact from the drivers or pressures they use to estimate impact. Tools should strive to ensure that there is alignment between the methodologies they employ, the output metric provided and the objectives of the tool. Limitations pertaining to lack of spatially explicit outputs (i.e., sector-generic outputs) for many tools are good examples. The Partnership for Biodiversity Accounting Financials elaborate an extended list of best practices for biodiversity footprinting tools specifically (PBAF, 2024). This can help users ascertain if the tool is best suited for screening potential impacts based on generic classifications of economic activity or for evaluating outcomes. The differences between these purposes and the ability of varying methods to support them are further developed in **Chapter 4, Section 4.4**.

When applying these tools, best practices include using asset-level information on location, emissions and resource use from direct operations if disclosed or captured by a business. Emissions and resource use can also be modelled from disclosures of comparable businesses or sectors, but then with added uncertainty of estimated values and with the added drawback of not being able to differentiate impact between businesses in a given sector. Evidence does not support the use of revenue data as a strong input to biodiversity footprinting.

3.4. Impacts of business sectors on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people

3.4.1. Best estimates for the impacts of business sectors on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people

No authoritative estimate currently exists that provides a quantification of the impacts of businesses on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people comparably across a comprehensive range of different sectors and using generally agreed upon metrics. Instead, there are a range of estimates of impacts associated with one or more industrial sectors, based on a variety of the methodologies outlined in **Section 3.3**. Such approaches typically focus on impacts on species, ecological communities and habitats, or measurement of drivers or pressures. They commonly use a combination of life cycle impact assessment and multi-regional input-output analysis or are derived from the International Union for Conservation of Nature Red List of Threatened Species data (IUCN, 2025) and other key global biodiversity datasets. Life cycle approaches aim to capture impacts across the value chain, whereas other approaches capture only the direct impacts of a sector. Relevant metrics in these cases include 'species.year', 'potentially disappeared fraction' of species, mean species abundance and metrics such as those based on the International Union for Conservation of Nature Red List of Threatened Species (Mair et al., 2021). The associated data – along with multiple additional datasets, e.g., Projecting Responses of Ecological Diversity in Changing Terrestrial Systems referred to with the acronym "PREDICTS" (Hudson et al., 2014) and landcover data – also provide the basis for risk and materiality tools such as ENCORE. The unit of analysis is typically sectoral or regional (i.e., by geography) and not at the level of individual businesses. It should not be assumed that only big businesses are relevant, or even dominant in terms of impacts. However, a number of the studies focus on the world's larger businesses, e.g., based on the Morgan Stanley Capital International (MSCI) World Index, or Global Fortune 100 (Zu Ermgassen et al., 2022).

Although there are a growing number of methods, approaches and tools for measuring the impacts of businesses on biodiversity (**Section 3.3**), these have not yet produced a definitive basis for comparison across all, or even most, sectors. Nonetheless, existing estimates provide an understanding of the likely relative impacts compared across those sectors with the greatest impacts on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people⁶. **Figure 3.3** provides an overview of the outcomes of some such known estimates. These estimates were identified based on a search of the scientific and grey literature for estimates based on the methodologies outlined in **Section 3.3**, with requirements for inclusion being that (a) estimates were quantitative, (b) two or more defined sectors were judged using a comparable methodology, and (c) the results were accessible.

Overall, the comparison across sectors in **Figure 3.3** provides support for the widely held view that sectors are not equally responsible for biodiversity loss. Existing quantitative studies consistently identify the agriculture, forestry and fishing sector (which includes all agricultural commodities) as a key driver of biodiversity loss, with studies assessing impacts focusing primarily on agriculture and forestry, and sometimes aquaculture. Energy (the electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply sector, although studies primarily assess electricity, oil and

⁶ Data management report referring to the review of cross-sector biodiversity impact estimates
<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17238915>

gas), construction, mining and quarrying, transportation and storage, and manufacturing are often highlighted as high impact sectors as well. There are important nuances and limitations to these assessments, such as the degree to which attribution for biodiversity impacts can be considered to rest fully with primary industries that support other sectors throughout the value chain, which are discussed further below.

Figure 3.3 Relative sector-level impacts from studies providing cross-sector estimates of impacts on biodiversity. Studies were selected according to inclusion criteria in the main text and re-categorised against the International Standard Industrial Classification of All Economic Activities (United Nations, 2008). Each source of analysis is given one column; the colour scheme provides a qualitative illustration of the relative impact or materiality by sector as extracted from that analysis. Darker shades indicate higher estimated impact within a study; white indicates sectors that were not assessed. Sectors are listed according to their weight across studies (high = 3, intermediate = 2, low = 1, not

assessed = 0). Sources A) (AGCS, 2018); B) (Irwin et al., 2022); C) (Finance for Biodiversity Foundation, 2022); D) (Sun et al., 2022); E) (UN Environment Programme et al., 2020) ; F) (Maxwell et al., 2016); G) (CDC Biodiversité, 2021a, 2021b, 2022b, 2022a, 2023c, 2023a, 2023b); H) (Mair et al., 2021); I) (CBD, 2014); J) (Salafsky et al., 2025); K) (Natural Capital Finance Alliance & UN Environment World Conservation Monitoring Centre, 2018)

3.4.1.1. Sector-level estimates from existing tools and methodologies

In **Figure 3.3**, estimates are split into those focusing on negative impacts to biodiversity and on materiality. Each category is discussed in more detail in turn.

The agriculture, forestry and fisheries sector are consistently identified as one of the sectors having the highest negative impact on biodiversity across many estimates. This is logical, given the spatial extent of agricultural activities and the contribution of land use change to species threat (Maxwell et al., 2016), as well as the sensitivity of some indicators to spatial pressures. For example, mean species abundance is a function of human pressures including land use, fragmentation and hunting, alongside three other pressures; see Kok et al. (2014). Manufacturing and utilities (energy and water) also have a relatively high impact on biodiversity across estimates, including across multiple biodiversity footprinting approaches (e.g., Finance for Biodiversity Foundation, 2024), which considers four different biodiversity footprinting approaches: the Biodiversity Impact Analytics powered by the Global Biodiversity Score (BIA-GBS) tool; the Corporate Biodiversity Footprint tool; the Biodiversity Footprint Financial Institutions tool; and the Global Impact Database tool; see **Section 3.3** and **Figure 3.3**). It is equally important to consider are the gaps in these assessments: none comprehensively include all sectors in the International Standard Industrial Classification (ISIC), leaving considerable areas for further evaluation (**Figure 3.3**).

Similarly, for impacts based on the International Union for Conservation of Nature Red List of Threatened Species, agricultural activities and hunting again represent the largest impacts, leading others associated with substantial impacts on biodiversity such as energy and the construction sector (Irwin et al., 2022; Mair et al., 2021; Maxwell et al., 2016). Red List data are mature, well-established and useful for many applications, representing one of the larger global biodiversity datasets available and enabling analyses based on the STAR metric (**Section 3.3**). However, Red List data are not taxonomically complete, and species assessments can lag substantially behind actual trends. Efforts are underway to broaden International Union for Conservation of Nature Red List of Threatened Species coverage across taxonomic groups and biomes to reduce such knowledge gaps. These include Red List assessments of all reptiles (Cox et al., 2022) and freshwater fishes, decapod crustaceans, and odonata (Sayer et al., 2025). Some high impact sectors are currently under-represented as pressures contributing to the Red List. For example, the impacts of sand mining on threatened species has been a gap on the Red List (Torres et al., 2022). The existence of such sectoral 'unknown unknowns' is important to consider more generally when interpreting sector-level estimates of biodiversity impacts.

An important consideration across the above estimates based on different methodologies is the issue of scope. For instance, life cycle impact assessment approaches consider both direct impacts and supply chain impacts and in some cases those across the full value chain. Conversely, the estimates based on Red List data (including the STAR metric) consider primary direct threats from the perspective of the relevant species, attributing threads to the primary industries (e.g., agriculture, extractive sectors) and not considering the sectoral end-users of the commodities produced by the primary industries. Addressing this, (Irwin et al., 2022) linked

STAR to the EORA multi-regional input-output database to estimate sectoral contributions towards extinction risk embodied in international trade flows (see the summarised results also in **Figure 3.3**). Another consideration is that leading approaches for estimating impacts on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people for different sectors, as outlined above, are focused on negative impacts. The Red List focuses only on species threat. Life cycle assessment approaches focus on reduction in biodiversity, which means when applied to agriculture, these would consider how pressures from agriculture reduce global biodiversity, but not capture any gains achieved within production landscapes. While it is clear that the agriculture, forestry and fishing sector has major negative impacts on biodiversity, existing studies have not captured to what extent this sector provides opportunities for biodiversity gain relative to current conditions and crucially, how that relates to opportunities in other sectors.

Similar sectors identified as having high impact are also identified as having high materiality. Materiality in this context follows the definition of the Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures (TNFD, 2023): how 'dependencies and impacts on biodiversity create risks and opportunities for an organization's financial position and prospects' (financial materiality, based on the International Financial Reporting Standards definition) and in terms of the 'information needs of stakeholders focused on impacts' (impact materiality, based on the Global Reporting Initiative definition). ENCORE (ENCORE, n.d.), a widely used tool for understanding materiality to businesses, rates materiality from low to very high across a range of sectors. Agriculture, forestry and fishing again ranks most highly in terms of materiality (NCEA & WCMC, 2018). These are followed by the energy and water supply sectors and, to a lesser extent, mining and quarrying.

3.4.1.2. Other sector-level proxies for impact

Sector-level estimates of drivers of biodiversity change – such as land and sea use, direct exploitation of organisms, climate change, pollution, and the introduction of invasive alien species – can also provide an indication of biodiversity impacts (e.g., Kulionis et al., 2024). It is important to emphasize that these are either drivers or pressures, and can be useful proxies for biodiversity impact, but cannot be used to directly measure a change in the state of biodiversity or nature's contributions to people. For example, energy, transport, industry (production of materials such as metals, chemicals and cement) and agriculture/forestry are broadly responsible for greenhouse gas emissions as a driver of biodiversity loss (e.g., Lamb et al., 2021). In turn, this supports the conclusions based on biodiversity metrics above. In some life cycle assessment analyses, greenhouse gas emissions have been seen to be closely correlated with biodiversity impacts – however, this tight correlation is only the case for a very specific set of economic activities and also may largely be due to limits in data availability related to the links between business activities and the other four driver of biodiversity change (e.g., Bull et al., 2022).

Sector contributions to land use change provide another proxy for biodiversity impacts. Spatial area alone (e.g., of different habitat types, land uses, etc.) is not a good representation of biodiversity value, but – especially given the importance of land use change as a contributor to biodiversity loss – spatial analyses can provide indispensable proxies. As part of this, it is worth noting the increasingly influential role that Earth Observation approaches are playing in tracking biodiversity impacts and dependencies, and the potential they have going forward, for example in relation to the Essential Biodiversity Variables (Skidmore et al., 2021). With sufficient access to sectoral value chain data and further development of appropriate biodiversity proxies, the potential applications of spatial analyses based on Earth Observation approaches are considerable. Such spatial approaches run the risk of overweighting the impacts

of agriculture and forestry, with urbanisation, construction and civil infrastructure also presenting major global land uses (FAO, 2022). Simple spatial approaches also have some important caveats, not least that some sectors have substantial impacts with disproportionately small spatial footprints, such as oil and gas or mining sectors, and major linear infrastructure. It can also be difficult to attribute land use change to certain sectors, such as finance and insurance.

3.4.2. Gap analysis

Information from existing assessments of sector-level business impact on biodiversity (**Figure 3.3**) demonstrates that multi-sector analyses are far from comprehensive. Having consistent analyses across all sectors will require filling gaps for certain sectors. This could also involve using multiple metrics to estimate impacts, to account for differences in scope, emphasis and methodology.

In addition, there is a notable gap in sector-level assessments of impacts on nature's contributions to people. Despite numerous assessments of the impacts of policies and scenarios on nature's contributions to people (e.g., Chaplin-Kramer et al., 2019; Pereira et al., 2024) business impacts on nature's contributions to people are less frequently assessed, whether at the level of individual business activities or sectors (but see Chaplin-Kramer et al., 2017; Mandle et al., 2024), and such assessments have not yet produced estimates that allow for a global comparison across sectors. Those sectors that might be prioritized for future research could include those with largest environmental impacts or those most critical to global value chains.

These knowledge gaps arise from several factors. First, business reporting of impacts does not sufficiently disclose impacts in value chains, whether highly material to the organization (e.g., in terms of physical or transition risks), or less material to the business but important to biodiversity. In turn, data from businesses and sectors cannot at present give an accurate assessment of the scale and magnitude of biodiversity impacts, beyond broad generalized patterns shown above. Second, many measures used to assess biodiversity (see **Section 3.3**) – and drivers of biodiversity loss – are best understood in relative rather than absolute terms. Eventually it will be necessary to move more consistently towards measurement of absolute impacts and dependencies (i.e., change in the state of biodiversity against a fixed baseline). This would not only facilitate wider benchmarking of impacts across sectors but would also be consistent with the concept of seeking biodiversity recovery in absolute terms as per the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework. Finally, many business disclosures are centred around drivers of biodiversity change, not the state of biodiversity itself and are not generally connected to theories of change that connect the drivers or pressures to change in the state of biodiversity. This is not inherently inappropriate, given the multidimensional nature of biodiversity and nature's contributions to people and therefore the multiplicity of ways in which they can be assessed. However, sector-specific standardized disclosures, combined with georeferencing, could generate the data needed for estimates of sector-level biodiversity and impacts on nature's contributions to people.

Overall, existing methods, approaches and tools currently provide the ability to measure the *relative* impacts of business on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people. The challenge now is to extend existing analyses comprehensively across all sectors, at scales from individual businesses to sectors and beyond and to evaluate impacts on nature's contributions to people from businesses more extensively. Global spatial datasets exist on land uses for agriculture, mining, forestry, built infrastructure and other key sectors, which could be combined with biodiversity data to estimate impacts (although access to both sectoral and environmental

datasets in terms of restrictions and/or the cost for licensing data, for some organizations, is an important emerging issue). In turn, these could be combined with input-output models to enable further estimates of the proportional distribution of impacts along value chains. An important element of all such analyses would be to capture assumptions made and associated uncertainties in estimating relative impacts, both within and between different methods applied. Nonetheless, knowledge gaps cannot be an excuse for inaction, as it is already clear that some specific sectors are major drivers of biodiversity loss due to their land use needs or physical resource requirements. This concern calls for fair and transparent reporting that addresses remaining gaps in reporting about the impacts of businesses on biodiversity.

3.4.3. Sector-level information on positive impacts of businesses on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people

Efforts towards the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework 2030 mission to put in place actions to halt and reverse biodiversity loss must begin with mitigation of the negative impacts discussed above. However, existing assessments generally do not incorporate estimates of positive impacts that business activities might have on biodiversity or nature's contributions to people. Positive impacts could include restoration actions (e.g., sustainable sourcing strategies, directly or via investment in biodiversity credits), restorative business models (e.g., agricultural practices that increase biodiversity or carbon sequestration), or as a result of nature-based enterprises for which biodiversity is a core focus (e.g., ecotourism). Biodiversity commitments have increasingly become a major aspect of corporate sustainability programmes (Lamont et al., 2023; zu Ermgassen et al., 2022a).

Positive impacts from businesses on biodiversity might include biodiversity enhanced or restored in production landscapes or landscapes managed for defense purposes (Qin et al., 2024). Some sectors may build business models around nature conservation and restoration, such as ecotourism and other recreational activities. Other businesses can reduce pressures on biodiversity through their core business, such as renewables businesses diverting energy use away from hydrocarbons (Sonter et al., 2024) or agricultural commodities diverting consumption away from animal products (Poore & Nemecek, 2018). A key issue is, however, the choice of baseline (Maron et al., 2018). For instance, renewable energy production may reduce biodiversity impacts in contrast to other forms of energy production but will still have some biodiversity impacts, so the choice of baseline determines whether the outcome of transitioning to renewable sources can be considered positive or less negative for biodiversity (Sonter et al., 2024).

In the case of nature's contributions to people, the IPBES Global Assessment of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services showed that business activities have increased material contributions that produce marketed goods, as evidenced by the increases in agricultural production, fish harvesting, bioenergy production, and the harvest of other natural materials over the past 50 years (Brauman et al., 2019). However, given global declines in the other 14 categories of nature's contributions to people assessed, these increases in certain material contributions are associated with losses of regulating and non-material contributions, such as pollination, pest regulation and soil quality. Regulating services are in decline partly as they are not typically priced or factored into economic activities and are more challenging to measure than natural capital stocks. Another priority is to improve their measurement.

Positive impacts of businesses on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people are not typically captured in any systematic way, and impacts of this type are currently small in

comparison to the negative impacts of business activities (UNEP, 2023). However, given both the potential and the necessity in relation to global policy of achieving positive impacts from businesses, these deserve more detailed consideration. One example of a means for capturing the full range of negative and positive impacts associated with businesses and biodiversity is provided by the Mitigation and Conservation Hierarchy (Milner-Gulland et al., 2021), relevant to structuring a nature positive economy as envisioned under the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework. Positive impacts will need to be understood and assessed alongside negative impacts to support a transition to an economy that delivers positive outcomes for biodiversity and nature's contributions to people (Leclère et al., 2020; zu Ermgassen et al., 2022a).

3.4.4. The informal economy and illegal activities

The biodiversity impacts of the informal economy and illegal activities are substantial. The informal economy includes economic activities that are not regulated by the government, often lacking formal contracts, worker protections, or taxation, such as small-scale farming, artisanal fishing, traditional crafts, street vending and other small-scale enterprises. Although the extent of informal and illegal mining is uncertain and varies by commodity and by geography (Maus & Werner, 2024), these activities have contributed to deforestation and to heavy metal pollution such as mercury and lead in soil, water and fish, harming the health of people relying on those resources (Caballero Espejo et al., 2018; Martinez et al., 2018; Ofosu et al., 2020). Deforestation and forest degradation from charcoal production has received much attention, especially in Africa, although the magnitude of impacts have been debated (Branch et al., 2022; Chidumayo & Gumbo, 2013). Many studies (reviewed in Ticktin, 2004) show that harvest of non-timber forest products, which may occur as part of informal economic activities, can affect ecological processes at many levels, from individual and population to community and ecosystem, with effects mediated by environmental conditions and management practices. IPLCs often engage in informal economic activities due to a combination of social, economic, cultural, and regulatory factors, including exclusion from formal institutions (Williams et al., 2015). IPLCs also have a susceptibility to harms from the negative impacts of the informal economy and illegal activities on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people given their close interrelationship with biodiversity.

The extent to which the impacts of the informal economy or illegal activities are included in global sector-level estimates discussed previously in this section or captured by the approaches and tools described in **Section 3.3** will depend on the methods used. The interface between the formal and informal economy and illegal activities is important to consider, given flows of materials between them. The informal economy's impacts are not easily traced or quantified through official statistics and data due to their informal status. The same is true for many illegal activities. Methods that rely on remote sensing for measuring the impact of activities, such as agriculture, mining, or logging, can capture the impact of some informal or illegal activities but may not distinguish them from activities that are part of the formal economy.

3.5. Connections to dependencies, risks and opportunities

In addition to businesses' impacts on biodiversity, businesses depend on a wide range of nature's contributions to people for their operations (see **Chapter 2**). These impacts and dependencies are interlinked, and the way businesses choose to manage their impacts and dependencies influences their risk and opportunity landscape. Mismanagement of dependencies can lead to significant negative impacts on both biodiversity and nature's contributions to people and on the business itself. On the other hand, effective management of business dependencies on nature's contributions to people can lead to a range of positive impacts. Furthermore, business impacts can affect their own dependencies, creating a feedback loop that can either enhance or undermine a business' sustainability and operational resilience. By understanding these pathways, businesses can take action to mitigate risks, enhance their resilience and pursue new opportunities.

3.5.1. Relationship between business impacts and dependencies on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people

While business dependencies on biodiversity are vital for their operations, if operations lead to environmental degradation and biodiversity loss, they may result in risks that make the business vulnerable. Such activities may lead to biodiversity loss with consequences for resilience of ecosystems and lead to changes in nature's contributions to people, with consequences for society. This is because businesses use natural resources, produce or consume products, own and manage areas of land, or finance other activities which have direct and indirect impacts on biodiversity. Businesses that rely on natural resources such as timber, fish, water and minerals may face scarcity due to over-exploitation, deforestation, overfishing and climate change. Industries such as forestry, pharmaceuticals, cosmetics and fisheries depend directly on biodiversity and also affect biodiversity through direct exploitation, habitat loss and pollution, ultimately affecting IPLCs (Mäkelä, 2017). For businesses that depend on nature's contributions to people such as pollination, water purification and soil fertility, whether directly or through their value chains, degradation of these benefits can lead to consequences including decreased agricultural productivity, higher water treatment costs, higher costs of inputs and lower overall efficiency. In the Dutch economy for example, over 45 per cent of the biodiversity losses related to business supply chains occur upstream of the direct suppliers (Wilting & Van Oorschot, 2017).

3.5.2. Nature-related business risks

Biodiversity loss has the potential to create business risks. This is the case whether these losses arise from a business' impacts on resources it depends on such as unsustainable harvest; business impacts that occur separate from its dependencies, such as from pollution or land conversion; or losses resulting from activities outside the business' value chain. A recent analysis showed that in the Dutch economy, 36 per cent (EUR 504 billion) in investments held by Dutch financial institutions are highly or very highly dependent on one or more ecosystem services (Retsa et al., 2020).

Potential threats posed to businesses that arise from their or wider society's dependencies and impacts on biodiversity are referred to as nature-related risks (see **Chapter 1**). Such risks can be categorized as physical risks, transition risks, and systemic risks.

Nature-related physical risks are risks associated with a change in the state of nature or biodiversity on which a business depends or is impacted by. These risks are usually location specific and can be acute or chronic. Acute physical risks occur as the result of specific, short-term events related to a change in the state of nature or biodiversity, such as crop pest invasions, flooding or wildfires. Pest and pathogen invasions are globally responsible for 40 per cent loss in crop yield and the disruption of species composition and structure of forest ecosystems that may affect businesses (Montgomery et al., 2023). For example, in 2020, the desert locust invaded the eastern African region putting at risk the economies of six nations and over 20 million people who faced severe acute food insecurity (FAO, 2020). Since locust outbreaks often follow floods and cyclones, such invasions may accelerate due to climate change (UNEP, 2021). This type of acute risk is therefore of significant threat to businesses that focus on cultivating, producing, or managing a single type of crop, plant species, or livestock. Among the acute nature-related risks, flooding is the costliest causing over €70 billion of economic losses globally in 2021 alone, and directly impacting households and businesses through the destruction of their assets (reviewed in (Endendijk et al., 2024). Flooding also has indirect ripple effects for society by destroying infrastructure and interrupting business processes and financial markets.

Chronic physical risks are related to gradual changes to the state of biodiversity. For example, invasive alien species may cause chronic risks through disruption of ecosystems. The Asian carp pose significant threat to commercial and recreational fisheries of the Great Lakes of North America (Stern & Upton, 2017). In contexts of water scarcity and/or competing water uses, access to fresh water can be a challenge. Inadequate mine water management involving high withdrawal, low rates of water reuse and discharge of contaminated water can heavily impact local water resources available to other businesses, as well as to IPLCs and other vulnerable groups (Lèbre et al., 2020).

Nature-related transition risks are the financial and strategic challenges that organizations face when not adapting to triggers prompted by changes related to policy, technological changes, shifts in consumer or investor sentiment and disruptive business model innovation (TNFD, 2023). Transition risk can be further subdivided into policy risk, market risk, technology risk, reputational risk and liability risk. Changes in the policy environment may arise from the creation of new policies or enforcement of existing policies to create positive influence or mitigate negative impacts on biodiversity. Businesses may face higher costs to comply with new policies, such as requiring investments in cleaner technologies, sustainable practices, or reporting frameworks. Increasing regulatory pressures may impose significant additional costs on businesses, such as carbon taxes (Becker et al., 2013; Chen et al., 2022). Perhaps most directly, businesses face market risk when loss of biodiversity or nature's contributions to people affects their ability to produce and sell goods and services, such as through disruption of supply chains and increasing costs of operations. This loss could be a result of a businesses' impacts on a resource on which it depends, such as unsustainable harvest or extraction, or it could result from the negative impacts of other actors. Businesses may also face market risk if customer or investor preferences shift in favour of products or brands perceived to have a more positive or less negative impact on biodiversity. Reputational risk includes social license to operate and brand value. Businesses with negative impacts on biodiversity or nature's contributions to people risk the erosion of goodwill from conscientious consumers who are increasingly demanding sustainable practices. Liability risks for businesses arise from factors such as increased regulation and litigation. Governments are increasingly imposing regulations related to biodiversity, potentially leading to additional costs for non-compliant businesses. Non-compliance can result in fines, litigation, and reputational damage.

Systemic risks are risks to a business that arise from the breakdown of the entire system and include ecosystem stability risks and financial stability risks. Climate change, land degradation, and pollution are systemic risks destabilizing ecosystems and disrupting business operations. Events such as extreme weather, pandemics and geopolitical shocks further strain natural systems and reveal the vulnerabilities of businesses that rely on them (Dasgupta, 2021). Financial instability – from market volatility and debt crises to geopolitical turmoil – also heightens these risks. During fiscal stress, some businesses may cut back on sustainability investments or exploit natural resources more heavily to protect short-term profits (UNEP et al., 2021). This behaviour can speed up biodiversity loss and ecosystem degradation, threatening long-term financial stability by undermining nature's contributions to people that many sectors depend on. Incorporating ecological risk into financial decision-making is therefore vital to break this harmful cycle.

3.5.3. Nature-related business opportunities

Nature-related business opportunities arise from opportunities to develop new products and services, as well as from management of impacts, dependencies and risks. Businesses have the potential to gain a competitive edge by addressing biodiversity loss through integrating sustainable use into their core strategies, driving innovation in products, services, and business models. Investments in protection, restoration and sustainable land management can provide cost-effective alternatives to grey infrastructure, while also improving ecosystem resilience (Grima et al., 2020; Vicarelli et al., 2024). Where new regulations or voluntary commitments lead businesses to track their impacts on biodiversity, this can open up new business opportunities to meet the demand for monitoring and reporting, such as utilizing technology to monitor and manage biodiversity impacts through satellite imaging, artificial intelligence, or blockchain for supply chain transparency.

Some nature-related business opportunities represent the flip side of nature-related transition risks. For an example of a market opportunity, businesses supporting biodiversity that develop innovative products and services could attract environmentally conscious consumers and tap into emerging markets. There are reputational opportunities, such as the potential for businesses to improve their value proposition and brand by responding to the growing public demand for products that minimize harms or have a positive impact on biodiversity, hence fostering consumer loyalty. Businesses that comply with regulations or anticipate forthcoming regulation can avoid litigation and minimize regulatory costs. Finally, biodiversity-focused businesses may find it easier to secure capital or have access to new sources of funds due to their good environmental performance.

3.5.4. Intersection of impacts, dependencies, risks and opportunities for businesses with Indigenous Peoples and local communities

Nature-related risks faced by businesses are multifaceted and are intrinsically linked to their dependencies and impacts on ecosystems, as discussed above. These interlinkages can also have a significant impact on IPLCs and their businesses, which are often deeply connected to biodiversity (Sarkki et al., 2023).

When businesses harm biodiversity – whether from overexploitation of natural resources on which a business depends or through impacts such as pollution or deforestation – IPLCs who also depend on that biodiversity may lose access to traditional economic activities and experience harms to livelihoods and well-being. For example, many agricultural practices harm

ecosystems and affect society at various scales, from IPLCs affected by pesticides in drinking water, loss of land for traditional food production, food security concerns, and reduced resilience to climate change (Laxman & Ansari, 2023; Liu et al., 2013; Parks & Tsioumani, 2023).

Business activities aimed at managing nature-related risks and minimizing or reversing impacts on biodiversity can also affect IPLCs. For example, as previously discussed in **Section 3.2**, biodiversity offsets meant to mitigate a business's impacts on biodiversity can prevent local communities from accessing that land and biodiversity (Bidaud et al., 2017). However, there are opportunities for businesses to mitigate the impact of their core business activities by working with local communities in ways that enhance biodiversity and livelihoods, such as by supporting more sustainable grazing practices (Ruckelshaus et al., 2019).

Collaborations between IPLCs and businesses and interweaving of Indigenous and local knowledge with business practices present an opportunity for addressing business dependencies, impacts, risks and opportunities in line with a more just and sustainable future. For example, revitalization of Indigenous agricultural systems, such as agroforestry, holds the potential to improve food security, enhance biodiversity and strengthen the well-being of Indigenous communities (Kurashima et al., 2019).

The intersection of business impacts, dependencies and risks poses a complex and multifaceted challenge that requires holistic solutions and sustainable practices informed by both social and natural sciences and with specific considerations for Indigenous and local knowledge (Hill et al., 2020).

3.6. Implications of business impacts for decision-making

Businesses’ impacts on biodiversity and nature’s contributions to people are multidimensional, whereby multiple pathways drive changes in the state of biodiversity (**Figure 3.1**), different impact typologies are used (**Section 3.2**), numerous tools and metrics are available (**Sections 3.3 and 3.4**) and the inter-relations between impacts, dependences and risks may vary between value chains (**Section 3.5**). This complex set of circumstances creates a range of potential implications, which vary across different groups of stakeholders and rights holders.

These inherent challenges make it hard to provide a robust, comparable and quantitative assessment of the impacts of businesses and different business sectors on biodiversity and nature’s contributions to people. This then potentially limits the ability to design and implement interventions needed by different stakeholders to effectively reverse the negative impacts and manage business activities required to achieve the 2050 Vision for Biodiversity. Based on the literature review and the key findings from this assessment, implications for each stakeholder group are discussed and summarized in **Table 3.2**.

Table 3.2. Summary of the implication of business impacts on biodiversity for different stakeholder and rights holder groups. Implications are derived from various sources summarised in the text.

	Governments	Businesses	Financial institutions	Civil society and consumers	Indigenous Peoples and local communities
Value and relationship with biodiversity	Transactional: impact & dependence	Transactional: impact & dependence	Transactional: impact & dependence	Cultural and transactional: dependence	Mutual interrelationship
Impact on stakeholders from business pressures on biodiversity	Natural capital erosion and loss or degradation of nature’s contributions to people that lead to economic costs, restrictions on growth and societal wellbeing. Loss of public goods at the expense of private benefits. Governance capacity loss and increased likelihood of policy failures.	Increased financial risks Disruption to supply and revenue due to loss or damage to natural capital. Reputational damage.	Increased financial risks and reduced rate of return on investments. Potential for stranded assets. Reputational damage. Market uncertainty.	Increased cost of living. Cultural ecosystem services loss. Increasing dis-connect with biodiversity. Life quality and well-being loss. Loss of biodiversity and financial option value (intrinsic and time value).	Direct impacts to ecosystem services used or upon which IPLCs relate. Cultural and spirituality impact. Life quality and well-being loss. Loss of access. Loss of biodiversity option value.

<p>Implications on the methodologies used to assess impacts to each stakeholder group</p>	<p>Insufficient inclusion of macro-economic impacts, measures and understanding of the effectiveness of decision-making policies and regulations in driving businesses to reduce biodiversity impacts.</p> <p>Need for consistent approaches and metrics in assessing and managing direct and indirect impacts.</p>	<p>Insufficient data or knowledge to inform business decision-making.</p> <p>Need to better assess and quantify direct, indirect and cumulative impacts.</p>	<p>Inadequate information to de-risk decisions due to insufficient comparable data on indirect and direct impacts at the company level across sectors.</p> <p>Lack of detailed understanding of the potential cumulative and in-combination risks across multiple investments.</p>	<p>Lack of inclusion of the impact (including health and wellbeing) in retail prices.</p> <p>Inability to recognize or understand business impacts on biodiversity.</p> <p>Insufficient information for informed consumer choice.</p> <p>Inability to determine whether there is fair distribution of costs and benefits of biodiversity loss.</p>	<p>Lack of inclusion of biodiversity-related cultural and spiritual values into assessments of business impacts on biodiversity.</p> <p>Incapacity to determine and address trade-offs.</p>
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3.6.1. Implications for governments

Governments, from local to national, are responsible for introducing and implementing appropriate and effective policies and regulations to address the drivers and pressures that impact the state of biodiversity resulting from business activities (Ferraro & Failler, 2024), as summarised in **Table 3.2**. Governments also face the need to balance economic and social outcomes with sustainable development and the integration of the three objectives of the Convention on Biological Diversity and the goals and targets of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework into national plans and sectoral policies. Governance quality is an important determinant of biodiversity loss, deforestation rates, protected area effectiveness and poaching (Barnes et al., 2016; Burn et al., 2011; Smith et al., 2003; Umemiya et al., 2010). Policy and governance tasks are challenging given the complexity and multiple pathways in which business activities contribute towards the drivers of biodiversity loss.

To be effective in addressing the impacts of businesses, the integration of business impact measurement and metrics across branches of government could be advanced to systematically capture knowledge regarding pressures on biodiversity from business activities, and to contribute to policy coherence (Fopa Tchinda & Talbot, 2024). Similarly, policy experiments that trial different systems of incentives or monitoring approaches (e.g., Bowles & Carlin, 2021) could generate practical experiences akin to real-world learning laboratories with higher likelihood for transforming the sector and associated stakeholders (Schlüter et al., 2023).

3.6.2. Implications for businesses

Appropriate mechanisms are needed for measurement and to incentivize businesses to make improvements to current modes of operation. Evidence points to significant knowledge gaps, implying that businesses are not implementing such actions (as summarized by Caro-Gonzalez et al., 2021).

Businesses need reliable and accurate data, particularly related to operations, and tools to better understand their impacts (**Section 3.4**) and to understand the linkages between impacts, dependencies, risk and opportunities (**Section 3.5**) (Carvalho et al., 2023). Both are critical to be able to set quantifiable incremental targets and implement adaptive management actions to drive transformative change (Addison et al., 2018); (Bull et al., 2014); (De Silva et al., 2019). Failure for businesses to measure and assess these impacts and dependencies also potentially undermines their ability to assess the resilience of their business models and strategies to manage biodiversity and impacts on nature's contributions to people, and their subsequent ability to deliver goods, services and financial returns. This failure will limit the capacity to operate within the boundaries of goals and targets of global frameworks (Kopnina et al., 2024), while respecting the rights and inter-relationships with IPLCs (IPBES et al., 2023).

A key tool by which businesses assess their biodiversity impacts and to a lesser extent dependencies, is through environmental and social impact assessments. However, environmental and social impact assessments alone cannot resolve global challenges of biodiversity loss and deterioration of ecosystem services. Typically, substantive trade-offs arise where negative impacts on biodiversity remain at the end of the environmental and social impact assessments process Gallardo & Bond (2023). In addition, due attention should be given to power imbalances and information asymmetries when IPLCs are involved as their traditional systems may suffer irreversible losses (Athayde et al., 2019; Heiner et al., 2019).

While there are few reviews on the effectiveness of environmental and social impact assessments globally, numerous projects or regional studies have illustrated their limited effectiveness (e.g., Kahangirwe & Vanclay, 2022; Omenge, 2023). No impact methodology or assessment fully takes into consideration the complexities of ecological systems (e.g., biodiversity, ecosystems, taxonomic groups, and essential biodiversity variables classes) (Damiani et al., 2023). In their imperfection, environmental & social impact assessments can also be politically manipulated and rendered ineffective: not learning from past mistakes continues to undermine the potential good environmental and social impact assessments can do (Athayde et al., 2019).

More recently, the increasing number of disclosure frameworks and standards (e.g., Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures, European Union Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive, Carbon Disclosure Project (CDP), Global Reporting Initiative), benchmarking (Nature Action 100, GIST), as well as an increasing number of agencies rating business performance in relation to biodiversity (e.g., Morgan Stanley Capital International, Sustain Analytics) (Billio et al., 2021) has been driving businesses to better understand their biodiversity impact. Yet, details on disclosures related to how businesses assess impacts can be limited (Machado et al., 2021), and there is restricted progress towards adopting measurable, time-bound commitments (zu Ermgassen et al., 2022b). Challenges associated with how businesses understand and act on biodiversity impacts are discussed further in **Annex 3.1**.

Scenarios and the application of the IPBES Nature Futures Framework (Durán et al., 2023) can be a key tool for businesses to enable understanding of ways to measure and assess potential

business impacts, business resilience and options for action by decision makers. Scenarios may be used to identify potential biodiversity impacts resulting from different investment decisions or business activities, which may then be used to determine the resilience of a business, its strategies, identify business risks and align with Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework goals and targets (Schlüter et al., 2023). It remains key to recognise limitations of global transition risk scenarios due to the complexity of ecological systems and insufficient data (Maurin et al., 2023). Scenario analysis at the local scale has been more widely used to inform local business decisions e.g., (Blatter et al., 2020; Di Pirro et al., 2021). Being able to consistently measure and assess business impacts is critical if scenario analysis is to be used to inform sector or corporate-level business strategies and plans.

3.6.3. Implications for financial institutions

Financial institutions cannot successfully de-risk their choices or identify emerging investment opportunities without understanding the risks, leading to their inability to innovate and transform the business sector (Flammer et al., 2023). Likewise, the lack of clear and systematic information regarding business impacts on biodiversity may significantly impede good decision-making. Similar challenges occur when aggregating impact data across a portfolio of investments, which precludes attribution of impact, for example if more than one financial institution has invested in the same project (Addison et al., 2019; Houdet et al., 2012; Stephenson et al., 2021).

There is a need for universality and consistency in the methodologies, tools and metrics used by businesses to ensure comparability, facilitate decision-making by financial institutions and shift of investments flows from negative to positive biodiversity impacts. At present, a majority of tools for financial institutions focus on initial screening of potential impacts and risks across their portfolio, rather than tools to assist decision making and derisking (Hadji-Lazaro et al., 2023; Svartzman et al., 2021), and use modelled or global datasets with limited resolution.

3.6.4. Implications for consumers and civil society

The economic value of biodiversity is well documented (Dasgupta, 2021; Sukhdev, 2010), as is the impact of biodiversity loss on the economy, livelihoods and society. Yet, consumers have limited information on the implications of biodiversity loss for their livelihoods, whether it may be related to the availability and cost of products consumers purchase (Cheng et al., 2024) or to the degradation of ecosystems and loss of species affecting food security, livelihoods, mental health and wellbeing (WHO, 2021). This interconnectivity between biodiversity loss and human development, cultural diversity, society and human behaviours is complex (Clark et al., 2014; Crist et al., 2017; Levis et al., 2024);

For consumers, the main implications associated with business impacts on biodiversity and nature's contributions to people are related to the price and availability of goods and services, while being influenced by business image and reputation. Negative externalities of business activities that harm biodiversity can lead to consumer and societal mistrust and apathy (Camilleri et al., 2023) and the likelihood of potential constructive alliances between consumers and businesses is reduced (Sanchez & Miller, 2024). Option value loss of biodiversity closes the door to future societal benefits including innovation and improved wellbeing (Agliardi et al., 2024).

3.6.5. Implications for Indigenous Peoples and local communities

For IPLCs the implications of business impacts on biodiversity are considerable due to their inherent interrelationships with biodiversity. Except perhaps for sustainable business models associated with IPLC businesses, activities undertaken by businesses may fundamentally conflict with IPLC culture and beliefs (IPBES et al., 2023) and have impacts on the resources and nature's contributions to people upon which IPLCs directly depend for their livelihoods.

Typical methodologies used by businesses to assess and subsequently manage impacts on biodiversity with consequences for IPLCs have improved but remain limited (P. McElwee et al., 2020; Yletyinen et al., 2022). Integrating inclusive and participatory decision-making processes (Herse et al., 2020), strengthening IPLCs rights and investing in community led nature-based business initiatives can mitigate the adverse effects of biodiversity loss and foster more resilient and sustainable societies while strengthening the participatory rights of IPLCs (IPBES et al., 2023) and addressing trade-offs (Van Rees et al., 2025).

3.6.6. Synergies and trade-offs in impacts and implications for decision makers

Decisions by governments and businesses will have synergies and trade-offs with other societal goals, including the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals and the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework. Positive progress towards certain Sustainable Development Goals at the expense of the biodiversity-related Goals (14 & 15) is well documented, as is the failure to meet any of the 2020 Aichi Targets (Buchanan et al., 2020).

Sustainable development policies have failed to reverse global decline in biodiversity and nature's contributions to people (Brownlie et al., 2013), which may be due to different values attributed to different goals whereby the loss of biodiversity represents a trade-off for socioeconomic gains resulting in continued ecological degradation. Given the best estimate of biodiversity impacts by sector and the need to meet the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework 2050 goals and 2030 targets, trade-offs need to be avoided to the extent possible (e.g., Gibson, 2006) if society is to make the transformative changes needed to meet the 2050 Vision for Biodiversity.

3.7. References

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